

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INFOGRAPHICS

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The article provides information about the importance of using infographics, their types, designs and advertising. It's explained in detail how it's important to all users, and how to present the information that's important to us in the best-looking format.

Keywords: *infographic, visual, image, content, blocks, Google Charts, designer, project, Online content.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНФОГРАФИИ

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В статье представлена информация о важности использования инфографики, их видах, дизайне и рекламе. Подробно объясняется,

насколько это важно для всех пользователей и как представить важную для нас информацию в наиболее привлекательном формате.

Ключевые слова: *инфографика, визуал, изображение, контент, блоки, GoogleCharts, дизайнер, проект, онлайн-контент.*

INFOGRAFIKADAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI

Sayidova Nazokat Sayfullayevna - BuxDU Axborot tizimlari va raqamli texnologiyalar kafedrasida dotsenti, f.-m.f.n.

Ostonova Nafisa Xikmatovna - Kompyuter tizimlari va ularning dasturiy ta'minoti (tarmoqlar bo'yicha) mutaxassislik magistranti

Maqolada infografikadan foydalanishning ahamiyatlari, ularning turlari, dizaynlari va reklamasi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Bu esa barcha foydalanuvchilar uchun ahamiyatli ekanligi, hamda biz uchun muhim bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni eng yaxshi ko'rinishdagi formatda qanday qilib taqdim etish to'g'risida batafsil tushuntirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *infografika, vizual, tasvir, kontent, bloklar, Google Charts, dizayner, loyiha, Onlayn kontent.*

Nowadays, it becomes complex and difficult for any designer to create visually beautiful works while encouraging their audience to take the valuable information they have. They have become a part of our daily lives, and now more than ever, our need for attractive, beautiful and at-a-glance infographics that fill everyone with interesting information is increasing day by day. In this informative article, we aim to reveal the role of infographics in helping us better understand the world around us. We use every minute of the day to imagine, think or plan.

The subconscious mind deals strictly with imagery - so it is a very powerful tool in conveying an idea quickly and effectively. In the same vein, when users need to share information effectively, they turn to a reliable tool - modern infographics.

Today, we can see infographics everywhere in various forms. In this article, we will discuss what infographics are, how they work, and what we should use them for we will explain. For this, first of all, we need to know what infographic is and what it means. So, the term "Infographic" itself comes from the abbreviation of the phrase "information graphics". Infographics help convey complex and detailed information in an easy-to-understand, visual format. A well-designed infographic uses images, data and text to tell a compelling and memorable story. Infographics help engage your audience by presenting a lot of information quickly. Listeners prefer to absorb large amounts of information more quickly than to read a block of text.

Now we will tell you why you should use infographics. Not only are large blocks of text and statistics difficult to read, but they can be more difficult to search online than infographics. Simplifying information through infographics allows listeners and readers to understand the main message at a glance. Also, people are more likely to remember your message clearly because it is easier to understand.

Infographics are very useful for marketing. A well-designed and attractive infographic will definitely help to establish you as an expert and master in your field.

Let's focus on content compression in infographics. Infographics turn information-rich articles, blogs, or reports into concise, visually enhanced information.

Now let's get acquainted with the types of infographics. There are many options for infographics and this informal visual delivery it can be said that with the development of new ways of giving, even more options will appear. Here we

mention a few.

Visual method. Sometimes we can do without text at all, this is known as a visual infographic. They are useful in guiding the presentation of the action. They can also communicate with the user, as well-designed visuals can be stimulating and pleasing to look at, but it is always advisable to stick to their functional purpose.

Time table. It is one of the oldest types of infographics. Timelines are a visual representation of the past. A simple timeline includes a chronological sequence of events, often in a specific time format supported by description. Other, more complex time frames may not follow a simple line, the family tree is a good example, using simultaneous events can make them more complex.

Statistics or data. For the uninitiated out there, statistics and data are where the brain meets vector lines to create amazing pie charts, graphs and charts. Combining two completely different worlds in this way can be very difficult. However, they can often be fascinating pieces of work, and by doing so, it can lead people who are not particularly interested in learning to take a second look at it and become more interested.

If you have all the elements to create an infographic, then a structure can bring it all together. Creating the right spacing and approach doesn't just look good, it's also listener andIt also provides a convenient design that students will like. In particular, there will be a combination of information and visual effects that must be perceived at the same time. It is also important to maintain a hierarchy so as not to confuse the user. You should always ask yourself what you should read first and what you should read last.

Let's get acquainted with the best tools for creating infographics. Understandably, making an infographic can be difficult to get right, but it can really boost your creativity as a result. Not only can you create great design, but you can also work well with information. For those who find it a little difficult,

there are other ways to solve this problem with some incredible tools that can help.

Miro is an online collaboration tool that helps you develop visual aids at home.

Genially is an online tool that helps you create interactive content.

Infogram is an online tool that helps you create infographics like interactive maps and reports.

Wepik is an online tool that lets you create directly from your browser using the countless resources available on Freepik.

SlidesGo is a great slide and presentation tool based on user-friendly templates.

With many similarities, infographics have two main functions: static and interactive.

Static infographics are a simpler solution to start with if your data and information is relatively unchanged.

Interactive infographics - although more complex in terms of programming and design difficulty, they stand out from the pack because they can appear more attractive and dynamic to the target audience.

Interactive infographics allow you to present your audience with constantly updated information while keeping your main story in the non-interactive parts of the infographic.

Let's get acquainted with the best tools for creating infographics.

Canva remains one of the most popular online design tools for creating marketing content - from brochures to ads to presentations and more. Its infographic creator is especially helpful when it's time to create your infographic. You can use free and paid design elements such as fonts, images and design palettes.

Like Canva, Google Charts is a great tool for developing and sharing

infographics. Unlike Canva, you can use Google Charts to create interactive infographic content on your website and share it with others. This infographic maker is completely free and easily customizable.

Kartograf - This free, map-based infographic tool creates interactive and visual maps without connecting to third-party mapping services.

With so many map types available, it's easy to present and share geographic data presentations, especially with Kartograph's Python library and JavaScript tools.

We need to maintain a good balance between text and visual elements. We can use icons, an image or a set of images to replace headings and separate blocks of text. In this case, it is advisable to use several different fonts.

The use of interactive elements is also important. Today's popular infographics attract attention with their interactive and animated features. While it might be a little more difficult to pull off technically, we think it's worth the extra effort. Because we believe that the result will definitely be favorable to the team.

The following mistakes should not be made when creating infographics.

While there is no hard or fast rule when designing an infographic, there are some guidelines to consider. In the following cases, your infographic will not be as impressive or effective.

Your infographic product looks the same as everyone else's. When using online content, it is very risky because it is similar to copying someone else's work.

It's like your infographic is poorly designed, i.e. clashing colors and unreadable fonts make your infographic less engaging.

In cases where there is a lot of text or it is too long, you need to make it meaningful and concise, always keeping in mind that the text you provide is for visual enhancement and improvement.

Decreasing content. Too much information quickly destroys the

effectiveness of a tightly edited infographic. You'll want to make sure you include the most important information your listeners and readers need to know.

Incorrect data entry. Not only does your content need to be accurate, but it's also important to be cited. When presenting facts or information, you'll want to make sure you include your sources somewhere in your infographic.

Once complete, you need to make sure the loose ends are tied up, making sure the final design is the right size for viewing. It is better if your infographic is larger or better quality, this is useful for listeners and readers who want to zoom in on the infographic to read the text or view the data.

When it's time to post your infographic on social media, target your audience and include the infographic that will most engage them.

Conclusions.

Infographics should play a huge role in getting your message across. Because they are popular and effective because they work.

Advances in animation and interactive elements have taken infographics into new realms. This field is constantly evolving, so trust me! It can be said that infographics exist, develop and share.

Don't be afraid to experiment with infographic types, designs, and advertising. Over time, you'll understand how best to present the information your audience needs in the format they prefer.

List of used literature.

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